

Evaluation Of Bamboo Leaf Ash As Supplementary Cementitious Material In Concrete

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Abstract

Utilizing waste materials possessing pozzolanic properties in concrete production has become a global trend. Evaluating the pozzolanic activity of materials that replace cement is gaining significance due to the growing demand for environmentally sustainable cement products. Incorporating Bamboo Leaf Ash (BLA) as supplementary cementitious material (SCM) in concrete aligns with the principles of sustainable construction by reducing waste, utilizing renewable resources, and potentially lowering carbon emissions associated with traditional cement production. In this research work, BLA is used as partial replacement for ordinary Portland cement (OPC) in ranges of 10%, 20%, 30%. Fresh and hardened properties of concrete were investigated. Experimental results showed that, Concrete mix with BLA gives satisfactory cube compressive strength upto the replacement level of 20% with OPC as binder. Beyond 20% replacement, cube compressive strength falls below the characteristic strength of concrete.

Keywords: Bamboo Leaf Ash (BLA), Manufactured Sand, Compressive strength.

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Introduction

Incorporating Bamboo Leaf Ash (BLA) as an extra cementitious substance in concrete presents an innovative and environmentally conscious approach within the construction industry. SCMs are substances that can be introduced into concrete to improve its characteristics and performance. BLA is one such material that has been investigated for this purpose. Bamboo leaves possess a high silica content, rendering them suitable for ash production. These leaves can be gathered, dried, and subjected to high-temperature combustion to generate BLA. BLA contains amorphous silica and other chemically active compounds that contribute to its pozzolanic properties. Pozzolanic materials interact with calcium hydroxide, a byproduct of cement hydration, to create additional cementitious compounds, thereby enhancing the strength and longevity of the concrete.

The incorporation of Bamboo Leaf Ash (BLA) into concrete offers several advantages, including enhanced strength, reduced environmental impact, and efficient resource utilization. The pozzolanic reaction between BLA and calcium hydroxide leads to the creation of additional calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) gel, which improves concrete's strength and longevity. By using BLA as a supplementary cementitious material (SCM), there is a reduction in the need for traditional cement production, a major source of carbon dioxide emissions. This, in turn, contributes to more sustainable construction practices. The specific proportion of BLA to be included in concrete mixtures depends on various factors, such as the desired strength, workability, and the intended application. To determine the optimal BLA ratio, it is necessary to develop mix designs through laboratory testing. Establishing proper testing protocols is crucial to ensure the quality and consistency of both the BLA and the resulting concrete mixtures. This entails evaluating properties like compressive strength, workability, and durability.

However, application of BLA in concrete impose some challenges. The chemical composition of BLA can vary depending on factors like bamboo species and burning conditions. This variability can affect the performance of concrete. BLA is not yet a widely recognized SCM like fly ash or silica fume. Therefore, there may be

challenges in terms of standardization and incorporating it into concrete design codes. Ongoing research is necessary to better understand the behavior of BLA in different concrete mixtures and environmental conditions. This research will help refine the utilization of BLA in construction. BLA can find practical applications in a range of concrete uses, including pavements, structural components, and masonry blocks. However, its application should be considered on a case-by-case basis, taking into account the specific requirements of the project.

Literature Review

In a study conducted by S.O. Odeyemi et al (2022) [1], the use of BLA as a Supplementary Cementitious Material (SCM) in High-Performance Concrete (HPC) was investigated. To produce BLA, bamboo leaves were subjected to calcination in an electric furnace at a high temperature of 7000°C. The resulting ash was analyzed using Energy Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence (EDXRF) and was found to exhibit pozzolanic properties, featuring a silica content exceeding 70%. The researchers experimented with replacing varying percentages (5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%) of cement with BLA by weight in the concrete mix. They subjected the concrete specimens created from these different combinations to tests measuring their compressive and splitting tensile strengths at intervals of 7, 28, and 56 days of curing. Notably, the study revealed that the highest strength was achieved when cement was substituted with 5% BLA after 56 days of curing. Microscopic examination of the concrete structures indicated that a 5% incorporation of BLA resulted in superior interlocking of concrete grains. Consequently, the study's conclusion suggests that it is feasible to replace 5% of the cement in High-Performance Concrete with BLA, thus enhancing the material's properties.

David O. Nduka et al (2022) [2] conducted an analysis of BLA, which was produced by heating dry bamboo leaves at around 600°C for 2 hours in a controlled laboratory muffle furnace. To assess the pozzolanic potential of BLA, they employed X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and scanning electron microscope/energy dispersive x-ray (SEM/EDX) techniques. Subsequently, they mixed BLA with Portland cement (PC) to create high-performance concrete (HPC) with BLA contents of 0%, 5%, 10%, and 15% by weight. The workability of fresh HPC samples was evaluated using a slump flow test. Over the course of 7, 21, 28, and 60 days of hydration, they measured the mechanical properties (compressive, splitting tensile, and flexural strengths) and durability characteristics (water absorption, sorptivity, and resistance to aggressive environments) of the HPC samples. XRF analysis confirmed that the calcined BLA exhibited pozzolanic properties, while SEM micrographs revealed irregular and angular morphologies. Incorporating BLA into the HPC matrix led to improvements in both the mechanical strength and durability of the tested samples, particularly when 10% of PC was substituted with BLA.

Blessen Skariah Thomas et al (2021) [3] conducted a comprehensive examination of recent developments concerning the integration of biomass ashes derived from agricultural waste into both OPC and geopolymer concrete. The study delves into the material characteristics of various biomass ashes with respect to properties of fresh and hardened concrete, encompassing aspects like mechanical strength and durability. The process of partially substituting OPC with ashes from various sources, was found to lead to a reduction in CO₂ emissions thus contributing to the mitigation of global warming. Furthermore, this approach aligns with the goals of zero-waste technology.

Lucas Henrique Pereira Silva et al (2021) [4] assessed the suitability of BLA (BLA) in mortar compositions, adhering to standard specifications. They carried out both chemical and physical characterizations using X-ray fluorescence, X-ray diffraction, and laser granulometry. To gauge the impact of BLA, mortar samples were subjected to compressive strength tests with cement replacements of 10%, 20%, and 30% by weight of BLA after curing for 7, 28, and 91 days. The pozzolanic properties of BLA were confirmed through the Chapelle test, thermogravimetric analysis, and X-ray diffraction. The results demonstrated that substituting cement with BLA up to 30% did not lead to a decrease in the compressive strength of the mortars.

John Temitope Kolawole et al (2021) [5] conducted an assessment of the suitability of bamboo leaves and clay brick wastes for use as sustainable components in cementitious composites. The premise behind this investigation was that the combined chemical compositions of BLA (BLA) and ground clay brick (GCB) had the potential to produce cementitious composites with sufficient strength and durability. To explore this, various combinations of BLA and GCB were mixed with Portland cement (PC) in ten different ratios, and the resulting binders underwent thorough characterization to confirm their suitability for use in cementitious composites. These binders were then integrated into concrete, and their performance was assessed. Additionally, their ability

to enhance the sustainability of concrete was examined. The findings revealed that, while GCB outperformed BLA, when blended at a 10% proportion each, they could achieve the desired strength and resistance to chemical deterioration.

Cecielle N. Dacuan et al (2021) [6] conducted an evaluation to ascertain the efficacy of introducing Bamboo Leaf Ash (BLA), referred to as BLASH, as either a Supplementary Cementitious Material (SCM) or an additive in conjunction with Portland cement. The objective was to improve the durability of reinforced concrete structures. Various specimens were prepared with mixtures containing 0%, 10%, 15%, and 20% BLASH, and they were reinforced with steel bars of diameters 16 mm, 20 mm, and 25 mm. In total, 100 cylindrical specimens were manufactured for this study. To simulate environmental conditions, these specimens were subjected to accelerated corrosion through impressed current techniques and a galvanostatic method. The results revealed that the specimens containing 10% BLASH exhibited superior performance, displaying longer times before corrosion initiation and propagation. They demonstrated increased resistance to acid penetration and reduced corrosion rates. Additionally, the crack parameters in specimens with BLASH admixtures, including crack width and frequency, were minimal. The inclusion of BLASH as an admixture enhanced the concrete's durability, improved its residual strength, and increased its overall serviceability.

Suvash Chandra Paul(2019) [7] provided an overview of the engineering characteristics of concrete made using commonly available agricultural waste materials. Research on replacing cement with agricultural waste materials has demonstrated significant potential for using them as partial substitutes for both cement and aggregates in concrete production. These waste-inclusive concretes exhibit mechanical and durability properties that are on par with or slightly better than those of OPC concrete. The successful integration of these agricultural waste materials into concrete represents an innovative approach to sustainable construction materials. It helps reduce waste generation and minimizes the demand for primary raw materials in cement production, contributing to environmentally friendly construction practices. This paper serves as a resource for the concrete industry in selecting appropriate waste materials and determining their optimal proportions for concrete production. Furthermore, the study identified research gaps that can guide further investigations into concrete formulations using agricultural waste materials.

Loic Rodier et al (2019) [8] presented a study focusing on the pozzolanic activity and hydration of cement pastes that incorporated sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA) and BLA . They investigated the pozzolanic activity of these ashes in both binary and ternary mixtures using electrical conductivity measurements. A kinetic-diffusive model was employed to quantify the pozzolanic reaction occurring between the ashes and calcium hydroxide solution. Additionally, they explored the impact of these ashes on the hydration of cementitious pastes through thermogravimetry analysis, X-Ray diffraction, isothermal calorimetry, and mechanical tests. The findings revealed that ternary mixtures of SCBA and BLA exhibited higher pozzolanic activity compared to binary mixtures containing SCBA alone. Both binary and ternary mortars demonstrated greater compressive strengths than the control mortar lacking mineral additives. Furthermore, the replacement of 10% of cement with SCBA and BLA led to a reduction in the content of calcium hydroxide and a decrease in the heat of hydration. Importantly, the study also indicated that the production of 1 ton of binder with agro-industrial ashes required less energy compared to conventional cement production methods. The results of the study suggest that incorporating agro-industrial ashes into binary and ternary blend cements can offer economic, technical, and environmental advantages for various industrial sectors, including the fiber cement industry, precast plants, and concrete producers.

Praveen Kumar Bannaravuri et al (2018) [9] studied the utilization of BLA as a reinforcement material in the fabrication of aluminum alloy composites. These composites were created using the stir casting process and underwent thorough characterization through various techniques, including optical microscopy, SEM with EDAX (Energy Dispersive X-ray Analysis), XRD (X-ray Diffraction), density measurements, hardness assessments, tensile testing, and dry sliding wear tests. The incorporation of BLA particles led to notable enhancements in both the hardness and tensile strength of the composites. Furthermore, the wear rate of the composites decreased with the addition of BLA particles, and the composite containing 4 wt% of BLA exhibited the best anti-wear properties. This strengthening effect in the composites may be attributed to an increase in dislocation density as the weight percentage of BLA increased. To gain insights into the tensile failure and wear mechanisms, the study utilized SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy) images of the fracture surface and worn-out surface morphologies of the composites. As a result of the addition of BLA (BLA) particles, the wear rate of the Al-4.5%Cu matrix alloy was reduced, with the composite containing 4 wt% BLA demonstrating the most

effective anti-wear performance. Overall, the inclusion of BLA particles significantly improved the hardness and tensile strength of the composites.

Evi Aprianti (2015) [10] conducted a comprehensive review with a specific focus on examining the possible use of agricultural waste materials as supplementary cementitious materials in the production of concrete. This work aimed to present the concept of incorporating these agricultural wastes by elaborating on their engineering, physical, and chemical characteristics. The review summarized the existing knowledge regarding the successful integration of agricultural waste materials in the concrete industry.

Moises Frias et al (2012) [11] conducted a study involving Brazilian BLA that was calcined at a temperature of 600°C under small-scale conditions. Various techniques, including XRF (X-Ray Fluorescence), XRD (X-Ray Diffraction), SEM/EDX (Scanning Electron Microscopy with Energy Dispersive X-ray Analysis), FT-IR (Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy), and TG/DTG (Thermogravimetric Analysis/Derivative Thermogravimetric Analysis), were employed for a comprehensive analysis of this ash. The research aimed to understand how this ash behaves in blended cements where 10% and 20% by mass of BLA was used. The findings revealed that this ash exhibited extremely high pozzolanic activity, with a reaction rate constant (K) on the order of $10^4/h$. The primary hydrated phase resulting from the pozzolanic reaction was identified as type I CSH gel. Additionally, the blended cements containing 10% and 20% BLA met the physical and mechanical requirements outlined in existing European standards.

Manasseh Joel (2010) [12] conducted an examination of the potential use of various agricultural waste ashes, including Acha husk ash (AHA), Bambara groundnut husk ash (BGHA), Bone powder ash (BPA), Groundnut husk ash (GHA), Rice husk ash (RHA), and Wood ash (WA), as partial replacements for cement in binder materials. The analysis of the results, which considered oxide composition, compound composition derived from Bogue's model, and laboratory test results, revealed that only when cement was partially replaced with 10% BPA did a noteworthy increase in compressive strength, by 7.14%, occur compared to using cement alone. A decline in compressive strength was observed when other agricultural waste ashes were used, and this was attributed to an increase in the SiO₂ component and a decrease in the CaO component within the mixtures of cement and agricultural waste ashes. To enhance strength, it is recommended to introduce lime into the mixture. Olugbenga O. Amu1 et al (2010) [13] conducted a study to examine the effects of stabilizing lateritic soil in highway construction using BLA. The research involved several tests to assess the characteristics of the soil and the impact of BLA addition. Preliminary tests were performed on samples labeled A, B, and C for identification and classification purposes, followed by tests to determine consistency limits. Geotechnical property tests, including compaction, California bearing ratio (CBR), and triaxial tests, were carried out on both stabilized and unstabilized samples by adding varying percentages of BLA (2%, 4%, 6%, 8%, and 10% by weight) to the soils. The results indicated that the addition of BLA led to improvements in the strength properties of the samples. The optimum moisture content decreased to 20.20%, 19.60%, and 9.32% with BLA additions of 8%, 4%, and 6% in samples A, B, and C, respectively. Moreover, the maximum dry density (MDD) increased to 1400 kg/m³, 1676 kg/m³, and 1941 kg/m³ with BLA additions of 8%, 2%, and 4% in samples A, B, and C, respectively. In terms of engineering properties, the unsoaked CBR values for samples A and B increased from 5.44% to 38.21% and from 11.42% to 34.99%, respectively. The shear strengths of samples A and B also increased from 181.31 kN/m² to 199.00 kN/m² and from 144.81 kN/m² to 155.90 kN/m², respectively. Taking into consideration these discoveries, it was determined that Bamboo Leaf Ash (BLA) holds significant promise for the stabilization of lateritic soils in the context of highway construction.

Objectives of the study

- To study the properties of concrete constituents such as OPC, BLA, and Aggregates.
- To examine how effects of BLA on the fresh properties of concrete.
- To explore the consequences of partially substituting BLA for cement on the compressive strength of concrete and determine the most effective replacement level.

Materials and Methodology

The materials used for the present study are as below.

Binder: OPC 53 grade, BLA

Coarse Aggregates: 12.5 mm natural aggregates.

Fine Aggregates: Manufactured sand.

Water: Potable water.

The M20 concrete mixes with varying proportion of OPC 53 grade, BLA as binders are designed and are tabulated as below.

Table 4.1 Concrete Mixes for the study

Mix Designation	Constituent Binders
100C	Ordinary Portland Cement
90C10BLA	90% OPC + 10% BLA
80C20BLA	80% OPC + 20% BLA
70C30BLA	70% OPC + 30% BLA

The methodology adopted to study the mechanical properties of concrete is as below.

Results and Discussions

Test results on concrete constituents are tabulated in table 5.1.

Table 5.1 Test results on concrete constituents

Concrete Constituent	Parameter	Test Result
OPC 53 Cement	Specific Gravity	3.15
	Standard Consistency	28%
Manufactured Sand	Specific Gravity	2.32
	Fineness Modulus	2.39
	Water absorption (%)	1.05
Coconut Shell Aggregates	Specific Gravity	3.36
	Water absorption (%)	20
	Bulk density, kg/cm ³ (Compacted)	790
	Shell thickness, mm	2-6

The slump of concrete mixes used in the study is shown in Fig 5.1. The cube compressive strength results obtained from the cubes of 150 mm x 150mm x 150mm size for the concrete mixes are shown in the graph 5.2. The split tensile strength results obtained for the concrete mixes are shown in the graph 5.3.

Fig 5.1 Slump of Concrete Mixes

Graph 5.2 Cube compressive strength of concrete mixes

Graph 5.3 Split Tensile strength of concrete mixes

Conclusion

Following conclusions were drawn based on the study.

- Higher replacement levels of OPC with BLA negatively influences workability of concrete as observed in slump. Replacement level beyond 20% is not advisable
- Concrete mix with BLA gives satisfactory cube compressive strength upto the replacement level of 20% with OPC as binder.
- Beyond 20% replacement, cube compressive strength falls below the characteristic strength of concrete.
- Usage of BLA in concrete leads to sustainability in construction with reduction in cost of concrete.

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